

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES THAT INCREASE MEDIA LITERACY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATION

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Abstract. *In this article, today, among other fields, the promotion of media literacy in the field of education plays an important role in increasing the effectiveness of the educational process. Today, life cannot be imagined without media, including the Internet. In the conditions of Uzbekistan's independence, the reform of the education system is primarily related to the implementation of advanced information technologies in the education and training system. Information culture is important in human development. Also, the article provides information on the basis for information technologies that serve to increase media literacy to overcome obstacles in the process of human development.*

Keywords: *information technology, media literacy, information culture, pedagogical technologies, Internet, threats, mass media, electronic libraries, sites, educational system, electronic networks, innovations, traditional methods.*

Nowadays, education cannot be imagined without media, that's why we all started using the term «media literacy and information culture». One example is that a personal computer has completely changed the possibilities of education. Internet laptops have created greater opportunities for the implementation of new pedagogical technologies in the educational system. In the conditions of Uzbekistan's independence, the reform of the education system is primarily related to the implementation of information technologies that serve to increase advanced media literacy in the education and training system.

Today, every student or student is required to develop and store information in education. Teaching using them in each educational institution makes it possible to use new foreign educational methods. A media literate student or student can complete huge tasks in a short time. It directly serves to improve the quality of education. At the same time, computer networks allow educational institutions in all parts of the globe to communicate with each other. For the educational system, this creates new opportunities for communication between teachers, students and students.

The uniqueness of information technologies that increase media literacy in the development of education is that from the point of view of human development, they penetrate into almost all spheres of human activity, they can be used for unlimited places and purposes. It is known that information technologies, media tools (television and Internet sites) allow to develop and store information and quickly distribute it through communication networks. Media tools bring people, their homes, and offices together and develop and complete a huge number of tasks in a very short period of time. This fundamentally changes the nature of information use and the structure of communication. At the same time, it allows communication with all points of the globe

in the educational system. For the educational system, this creates new opportunities for communication between teachers, students and students.

The uniqueness of media literacy is that from the point of view of human development, they penetrate almost all spheres of human activity, they can be used for unlimited places and purposes. Such technologies allow to overcome obstacles in the process of human development with great efficiency that did not exist before in three directions:

overcoming obstacles to acquiring knowledge. The use of information is of great importance for the formation of human opportunities for education. If education leads to the development of cognitive skills, information is needed to ensure a meaningful aspect of the knowledge acquisition process. Internet and “World Wide Web ” serve as the same information search channel for people of all social strata;

eliminates obstacles to participation in social life. The ability to communicate with the whole world through the Internet has made it possible to spread many global citizenship initiatives in recent years. For example, the act of providing feedback in the education system. Eliminates obstacles to expanding economic opportunities. Information and communication technologies and related fields and the educational system are the most rapidly developing sectors.

Globalization of the educational problem of information technologies that increase media literacy – from conducting seminars to revealing the essence of terrorism and religious extremism – increases the importance of information and educational opportunities of electronic networks. New information technologies allow to connect science and education with closer and more effective channels, such as conveying, supplementing and re-evaluating accumulated knowledge. Today, science – is the main, dominant tool for the development of this educational system. This was not always the case, with advanced media tools changing the importance of science in the education system. Society creates a new scientific structure not only related to the development of science itself, but also to the education and training system. The future of education. Currently, there are approximately 2.5 billion unique web pages on the Internet, and another 7.3 million new ones are added to their ranks every day [1].

Today, the number of personal computers that provide wireless Internet connection, including mobile phones, has exceeded the number of personal computers that connect to the Internet. Currently, the world volume as a result of the use of media tools in the educational system is 233 billion. is a dollar. As the number of learners increases, information technology is limited only to the possibilities of human imagination. The problem of educating a perfect, well-rounded person requires the education system to form a desire from the young generation to acquire not only the achievements of national culture, but also the achievements of universal information culture. The idea of educating a perfect person is one of the priority ideas of national independence. It is the task of increasing the quality of education, the level of spiritual and ideological education. The implementation of the national personnel training program must be based on new information technologies. Civil society cannot be built without encouraging the education system. The educational system should consist of a continuous process, not a static system of closed points of view, views. In order to guarantee the development of our independent Republic, the education system must be dynamic and perfect.

Information technologies that increase media literacy are a constant process of re-understanding personal thinking, developing new educational programs, and constantly exchanging ideas. In the era of current media networks, the features of creating and distributing

new technologies are changing, and this is happening in the following directions: first, skills are more important than ever in the modern global market, which is characterized by high competitiveness. Technology transfer and distribution is a very complex process. Secondly, the development of new global norms reflecting the recognition of the value of technologies is also becoming of great importance.

Overcoming the educational problem by promoting media literacy - from conducting seminars to revealing the essence of terrorism and religious extremism - increases the importance of information and educational opportunities of electronic networks. New information technologies allow to connect science and education with closer and more effective channels such as conveying, supplementing and revaluing accumulated knowledge. Today, science is the main, dominant tool for the development of the educational system. This was not always the case, modern media technology has changed the importance of science in the educational system. Society creates a new scientific structure not only related to the development of science itself, but also to the system of education and training. The future of education. Currently, there are approximately 2.5 million unique web learning pages on the Internet, and 730 new ones are added to their ranks every day [2].

The new rules approved by almost all countries are strengthening the regimes for the protection of intellectual property everywhere. They are manifested in the following. First, the private sector plays a leading role in the field of scientific research and experimental design worldwide. A large part of the financial resources, knowledge and personnel necessary for the development of new technologies is concentrated in this sector.

Secondly, a global labor market will be formed, providing employment to the most highly qualified technical specialists.

Thirdly, new companies, research laboratories and financiers, as well as corporations, are merging into global centers for the production of new technologies.

As a result, a new dynamic environment is emerging that ensures the necessary mutual relations between scientists, financiers and entrepreneurs. Get the best from different countries in such centers.

The best scientists and entrepreneurs from different countries are working in such centers, which creates great opportunities to attract investors. Investors are also interested in these works. The role of information technologies that increase media literacy in the development of education is clearly manifested in the multifaceted and complex process of mental work, activity and creative thinking of our teachers and students. Improving the effectiveness of the lesson is inextricably linked with the establishment of the educational process on a scientific basis and the practical application of new pedagogical technologies. The main goal of organizing media education in higher education institutions is to ensure the consistency of cooperation between teachers and students and to establish it in a specific goal-oriented manner. In this work, both pedagogical and technological management issues are solved. It should be noted that the participants of pedagogical innovations should thoroughly acquire methodological, pedagogical and technological knowledge about the laws of the process of emergence, manifestation and management of innovations. Otherwise, media companies alone will not give effective results.

In our opinion, based on the effectiveness of the tools that serve to increase media literacy in the educational system and the requirements of the modern world, the quality of training of specialists in higher education institutions depends on the conditions for the development and

implementation of the plan for conducting classes with the help of media tools, the traditional methods of education depend on proper application. As a result of the use of media tools, there are cases of abandoning traditional methods that are effective in some cases. This shows the high role of information technologies that increase media literacy in the development of education. Therefore, it would be better if the positive experiences of the traditional education system were combined with media materials.

«The concept of media literacy» covers the methods of improving knowledge acquisition by using factors that increase educational efficiency, designing and applying various pedagogical processes using the possibilities of information technologies. «The role of media literacy-enhancing information technologies in the development of education is understood as the management of the process of creating, receiving, evaluating, mastering and implementing various pedagogical innovations through media. The conditions and opportunities created in higher education institutions have been adapted to introduce the latest media samples, which serves to strengthen the creative activity of teachers and students [3].

Information technologies that increase media literacy are innovations and changes in the activity of teachers and students in the pedagogical process, which require the use of interactive methods in its implementation. Interactive methods are based on the activity of each student participating in the educational process, free and independent thinking. Learning using these methods becomes an interesting activity for the student. When interactive methods are used, students acquire the skills and abilities to work independently with the help and cooperation of teachers. Students acquire new knowledge on the basis of scientific research, research, and conducting experiments. The principle of acquiring knowledge through science is followed.

The importance of media literacy-enhancing information technologies in the development of education is given not to one student, but to all members of the group. Each member of the macrogroups feels the effectiveness of the media tool in completing the task. This situation forms media literacy in students and increases their initiative. The main form of organizing the educational process is the lesson. Currently, various non-traditional forms of the lesson are being introduced. Such lessons include the skills and abilities to develop the student's creative abilities, strengthen his mental potential, expand his scientific outlook, and be able to quickly and fully accept every innovation. The use of information technologies that increase media literacy in the course of the lesson arouses students' interest in scientific research, develops creativity and creativity. As a result, acquired knowledge, skills and abilities are applied in practical activities, and the quality of mastery increases. For this, the teacher should be skilled and create media materials depending on the content of the topics, and achieve active and conscious work of all students during the training.

The role of media literacy-enhancing information technologies in the development of education is especially reflected in computer work, searching for and absorbing relevant information from network networks. Only this requires perfect media literacy. This is also a modern activity that requires students to acquire special knowledge, skills and qualifications. It would be better if the students were taught the skills and abilities of working on a computer, and the information culture in this direction was also developed. It is necessary to focus the attention of the team of higher education pedagogues to direct innovations in the computer network for education.

Media literacy tools are aimed at serving to solve a certain number of tasks. If, along with solid knowledge, the student acquires the skills and abilities to use it in practical activities, if it is tested in the experiment, it achieves success, if the existing situation is changed in a positive direction, if work is carried out on a new idea, what kind of problem if the solution is imagined in detail, if it is thought on a global scale, innovation will give a guaranteed result. In the same way, the media literate person solves the task of raising a well-rounded, well-rounded generation.

Each of the problems listed above has a global scale and is partially reflected in modern didactics. However, general, «off-topic and objective questions can be distinguished. Thus, with the help of information technologies that serve to increase media literacy, it is necessary to design the lesson taking into account certain didactic methods and scientific-methodical situations filled with the help of traditional didactic and media tools. The most important of them is the systematic condition that can be solved using a problematic macro- and micro approach [4].

To see the lesson being designed in macroanalysis as a part of general education is kechong. Its goals and tasks are determined based on this, that is, the main tasks of science (mainly based on the nature of the field) come to the fore. And microanalysis requires that the planned lesson be accepted as a whole consisting of many components of the educational process (teacher, student, educational media) and the diversity that connects these components (that's why the lesson «planning is not » planning«, we say » design ish). At the same time, these connections seem more complicated than in traditional education.

It should not be forgotten that according to the purpose and didactic structure of information technologies that increase media literacy in the development of education, it is a very mobile and flexible type of education organization, it is in constant development, external (availability of material base, new tools) and internal (the state of the main components of the educational process) changes depending on the conditions. Therefore, taking into account the development, the lesson being designed should be able to expand and update.

In short, the relevance of the principle of media literacy in education is explained by several factors. If we look at the principles of information search, collection, storage, processing, change, distribution and use, from the point of view of science – media literacy and information culture, which studies its laws, we can compare voluntary pedagogical technology to information technologies, because it has a source (pedagogue), and an information receiver (learner). The use of new media tools in the educational process has fundamentally changed the evaluation system, which until recently was measured only by the ability of teachers to deliver information to the student. Today, the teacher's education is determined not only by his communication skills, but also by the level of media literacy and information culture. From this point of view, it is very important that the teacher's analytical, projective and prognostic abilities aimed at evaluating the quality of electronic educational resources (TER) and the effectiveness of their use in the educational process are formed. The scientificity and ease of presentation of the information presented in TER, the student's ease of learning, etc. should be evaluated based on general didactic principles. The use of modern media and pedagogical tools in education develops independent thinking, curiosity, manners, creativity, communication and aesthetic skills based on the student's hearing, vision, and what he sees.

In our opinion, the effectiveness of the use of information technologies that increase media literacy in the educational system and the quality of training specialists in higher education institutions are based on the conditions for the development and implementation of pedagogical

innovations, and the appropriate organic application of traditional methods of education through our implementation, we will undoubtedly achieve our goals.

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